

Role of Life Skills Education in Empowering Adolescent Girls

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Abstract

Life skills are the abilities that enable humans being to deal with the challenges of life successfully. They are also called psychosocial skills which encompass belief, thought process and behavioral method. Adolescence age is a change period of development and they are considered the creative members of a society because in this age not only their intellectual but physical and potential are very high. It is in this context, life skill education aims to provide adolescents with strategies to make healthy choices that contribute to a meaningful life. Life skill facilitates a complete and integrated development of individuals to function effectively as social being. Developing life skill helps adolescents in translating knowledge; attitude and values that makes their life fruitful and purposeful. With life skill education, adolescent make rational decisions in solving each problem or issue as it arises. This study attempts to assess the status of knowledge and practice of life skills among adolescents girls in Haryana. Students of government school situated in B P S Women's University, only women university in North India, is taken for this study. The overall objective of the study is to identify the status of knowledge and practice of life skills among the adolescents girls. Specific three life skills namely critical thinking, decision making and effective communication were studied. Focused group discussion with teachers was also conducted to understand the practice of life skills among the adolescents girls. The study revealed that low level of education and awareness among the parents are the main reasons because of which there is low level of life skills practice among adolescents. Deep rooted culture and belief systems play an important role in getting knowledge and practice of life skills among the adolescents girls. There is a need of life skills education for building a strong foundation for future generation.

Keywords: Life Skills, Adolescent Girls, Haryana, Education, Gender Equality, Development

1. Introduction

Globally, life skills education has been accepted as a significant component of adolescent development. Research from various countries has revealed that with life skills education not only enhances academic performance but emotional well-being, and resilience among adolescents also increased among adolescents. For example, a study by UNICEF in the year 2019 highlighted that life skills programmes in schools considerably improved students' self-esteem and capability to cope with stress and peer pressure. In developed countries, life skills education remains an integral part of the school curriculum, particularly to prepare students for the challenges of adulthood, career inclination and social integration. Life skills education is paramount with an increase of adolescent's population at the global level. According to the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), the global adolescent population (ages 10-19) stands at approximately 1.2 billion, accounting for about 16% of the total world population. This major demographic group is at a significant stage of development, with many opportunities and challenges that will shape their futures. Their well-being and development is also important from the global development goals perspective. As mentioned in the report of UNICEF which is working to engage and empower around 350 million adolescents in South Asia who are the next generation of leaders and change makers. There are nearly 350 million adolescent who live in South Asia. As adolescents is the age between childhood and adulthood and they face many challenges and fears in their lives. Despite of huge young demographic, adolescents in South Asia are mainly unseen and voiceless. They not only have limited information but also have little say in decision making affecting their life. There is no doubt that adolescence is the age full of opportunities and challenges. They have the potential to become the change makers. But due to the societal structure that is patriarchal particularly in South Asia where both girls and boys understand adolescence in a different way. For instance, girls face more challenges in their mobility, decision making and making their choices with regard to education and marriage.

In India, adolescents form a considerable portion of the population. As per the 2011 Census, there are about 253 million adolescents in the country, which constitutes around 20.9% of the total population. This population is paramount for India's future, both in terms of economic development and social progress. There is a need to address the issues pertaining to adolescents such as education, health, and skill development for their holistic development. In recent years, life skills education has gained importance in India. Various government and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have been implementing various programmes and schemes in order to empower adolescents. The National Curriculum Framework (NCF) 2005 focused on the importance of life skills education for the holistic development of the children. Though the studies revealed that implementation of such programmes are more evident in urban areas rather than rural areas. As per the National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA, 2020) report that efforts are being made to integrate life skills education in school curriculum, in urban areas but due to the lack of resources and trained staff, life skills programmes and schemes are not able to deliver expected results. Previous studies have shown that while there are efforts to promote life skills education in Haryana, these are hampered by cultural conflict and limited resources.

Due to the socio-cultural framework, Haryana faces distinctive challenges in implementing life skills education in schools. The state has one of the worst sex ratios in India, with 879 females per 1,000 males as per the 2011 Census. This gender imbalance has intense implications on the status of women and girls in society. Traditional gender roles and the belief of early marriage are some of the upmost challenges that limit the girls to access education and opportunities for their development. Not only that, issues such as gender-based violence, inadequate reproductive health services, and economic restrictions become stumbling blocks in the way of empowering adolescent girls. Thus, adolescent girls in Haryana face a unique set of challenges and essential life skills are must for their overall development. These skills, as identified by the World Health Organization (WHO), are vital for enabling young women to find a way in the complexities related to their social, economic, and personal lives.

2. Objectives and Methodology

This study investigates the awareness about the life skills education among adolescent girls in Haryana. Attempt has been made to explore the challenges faced by girls in practicing life skills education. Focus group discussion was conducted with the adolescents girls studying in 12th grade of the government school in B. P S women's University, which the first women university in North India. One to one interview, focus group discussions observation etc were conducted with students to in order to identify their understanding on life skills education. The paper concludes with recommendations for policymakers, educators, local self governments and community leaders to enhance life skills education for the holistic development of adolescent girls.

3. Definition of Life Skills

Life skills are recognized as a set of abilities that cover cognitive, emotional, and interpersonal elements that are instrumental for building capacity of the individuals to find a positive way in the complex world. These skills are vital not only for the personal development but also required for effective functioning in the society at large. According to World Health Organization (WHO) life skills are those capabilities that enable individuals to deal successfully with the challenges of daily life. This definition focuses on the importance of life skills that are instrumental in helping the people to maintain positive approach towards life despite of facing challenges in life. WHO classify life skills into core areas such as Decision-making and Problem-Solving, Creative and Critical Thinking, Effective Communication and Interpersonal Relationships, Self-Awareness and Empathy and Coping with Emotions and Stress. Life skills are one step further in application of the academic knowledge in the practical real life situations. They help in empowering people to live their life to the fullest and interact with the people positively. In order to practice life skills education, it is important to acquire knowledge, way of thinking, problem solving approach and good decision making. Following are the major components of life skills education:

3.1 Critical Thinking: Critical thinking means ability to think clearly and wisely. It also involves making decisions based on considering various perception and evaluating

information. It also means making logical conclusions based on the existing facts. It is a valuable skill in various aspects of life starting from academic research to everyday decision-making. It is helpful in finding a solution of a complex problem and making well-informed choices. It also encompasses to think out of the box and create innovative ideas for finding solutions to the problems. Creative thinking is important for both personal and professional growth.

3.2 Decision-Making: Decision-making is the course of action of choosing the best action from various alternatives. It also means taking a decision after understanding the consequences of each action and select the best option that in tune with the values, ethics and life goal.

3.3 Problem-Solving: Problem-solving is an art to identify, analyze, and find solutions to problems of life. It needs an organized approach to understand the root cause of a problem, find out and implement the best possible solution of the problem.

3.4 Emotional Life Skills Emotional life skills involve the capability to identify, understand, and manage one's and others emotions. These skills are vital for emotional intelligence, which is the basis for building strong relationships and lead a balanced life. Self awareness, emotional regulation, empathy etc. are part of emotional skills that are also used in the interpersonal life skills. They are instrumental in effective communication, build and maintaining relationships with others. These skills are necessary for social skill, teamwork, and leadership.

4 Challenges faced by adolescent girls

Adolescent girls face many challenges across the globe due to socio, economic, cultural, and political factors. These issues are prominent particularly in those countries where gender inequalities are more deep-rooted in their culture and societies. Some of the challenges faced by adolescent girls because of which education of life skills are not much practiced. After conducting focused group discussion with school students, it was found that while a majority of the girls were aware of the concept of life skills. Rural girls, in particular, showed lower levels of awareness about life skills education. Following are some of the challenges being faced by adolescent girls

4.1. Education

Latest statistics with regard to education, according to UNESCO, 129 million girls worldwide are out of school, including 32 million of primary school age, 30 million of lower-secondary school age, and 67 million of upper-secondary school age . Lack of education is the important factor which not only limits opportunities for girls but also lead to higher rates of child marriage and poor health effect. Research conducted in this area revealed that girls who obtain secondary education are six times less likely to marry as children compared to those who receive little or no education . Many schools, especially in rural areas, lack the resources to effectively teach life skills. This includes a shortage of trained teachers, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of educational materials. Many schools, particularly in rural or underserved areas of Haryana, may lack the necessary resources to effectively implement life skills education. This includes a shortage of trained educators, educational materials, and proper facilities. Without adequate resources, even well-designed programs may fail to reach their full potential. Teachers may struggle to deliver the curriculum effectively, and students may not have access to essential learning materials.

4.2. Child Marriage

According to the latest statistics of UNICEF reports that approximately 12 million girls under the age of 18 are married each year. Child marriage often lead to early pregnancy, school dropout, and increased risk of domestic violence. It continues the cycle of poverty and become a major stumbling block for limiting girls to access opportunities for their development. Child marriage is the important factor particularly for adolescents girls because of which they are not able to achieve their dreams and understand their full potential. Child marriage often leads to early school dropout and girls are conditioned to take care of the household responsibilities, which disturb their education. Early marriage also make women financial dependence on their family members that further limit their ability to make independent choices.

4.3. Health

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), problems related to pregnancy and childbirth are the major reason for the death of the 15 to 19 year old girls across the globe. In

addition to this, nearly 21 million girls aged 15 to 19 years and 2 million girls under 15 years become pregnant in developing countries each year. Early pregnancy is linked with severe health risks for both the mother and child, including higher rates of maternal mortality, low birth weight, and neonatal mortality. Adolescent girls also face higher risks of sexual and reproductive health issues, including sexually transmitted infections (STIs) like HIV.

4.4. Violence and Exploitation

Research reveals that one in three women worldwide experiences physical or sexual violence, and adolescent girls are mainly vulnerable. There is no denying fact that violence and exploitation have long term psychological, physical, and social consequences on adolescents. The pervasive issue of gender-based violence in Haryana further exacerbates the challenges faced by adolescent girls. Fear of violence, both within and outside the home, restricts girls' mobility and participation in educational activities.

4.5. Gender Inequality and Discrimination

The Global Gender Gap Report 2023 by the World Economic Forum highlights the persistent gender inequalities, particularly in terms of economic participation and political empowerment. Adolescent girls in particular face discrimination in many societies which limit their opportunities for growth and development. Gender inequality blocks the way for girls to access education, healthcare, and employment opportunities. It also gives birth to other issues such as child marriage and violence.

4.6.Cultural Resistance: Traditional gender roles and societal expectations often limit girls' ability to practice life skills, particularly in rural areas. For example, girls are often discouraged from expressing their opinions or making independent decisions, which undermines their confidence and self-esteem. In Haryana, traditional cultural norms and values can significantly impact the acceptance and implementation of life skills education. Communities may view certain life skills as unnecessary or contrary to established social norms, particularly in conservative or rural areas. This resistance can lead to a lack of support from families and communities, which can undermine the effectiveness of life skills programs. Adolescents may not receive the necessary encouragement or resources to engage in these programs.

4.7.Economic Constraints: Economic barriers also play a significant role in limiting access to life skills education. Girls from low-income families often prioritize household responsibilities and economic activities over education, leaving little time for life skills training. Economic barriers can affect both the implementation of life skills education and the participation of students. Low-income families may prioritize immediate economic needs over educational programs, and schools in economically disadvantaged areas may lack the funding to support life skills education. Economic constraints can limit the availability of life skills programs and prevent students from participating fully. Families may be unable to afford additional expenses related to these programs, and schools may struggle to maintain these initiatives without sufficient funding.

5. Government Initiatives for empowering adolescent girls

Though a lot of efforts have been made by both Central and State government to empower adolescent girls in order to address gender inequalities and barriers that hamper their development. Governments implement programmes in areas like health , education, employment so that gender gap in the society can be reduced and girls have the same opportunities as boys. Through the scheme and programmes implemented by the government cultural norms and practices that perpetuate gender discrimination and restrict girls' opportunities are challenged. Following prominent programmes and schemes are being implemented by government for empowering adolescent girls.

5.1 Haryana Kanya Kosh

The Haryana Kanya Kosh scheme is a programme started by government of Haryana to empower and develop the girls of the state. It highlights of providing an environment where girls have equal opportunities for growth and development. The scheme in general involves providing financial assistance, educational support, and resources to facilitate young girls to follow their dreams and defeat barriers in their path towards development. The Haryana Kanya Kosh scheme is planned to build a more just society by providing a supportive environment for

young girls towards their bright future. This scheme is also instrumental in creating a safe environment where girls can empower themselves.

5.2 Aapki Beti Hamari Beti

"Aapki Beti Hamari Beti" scheme is a major initiative taken by the Haryana government to promote gender equality and empowering girls in the state. It was started in 2015 with an aim to encourage families to educate and support their daughters by providing financial incentives and support for various needs. The scheme offers financial support to families for the education and welfare of their daughters. This includes a one-time financial incentive for families who enroll their daughters in schools and ensure their continued education. Scholarships are provided to girls for pursuing higher education, helping to reduce the financial burden on their families and promote further educational opportunities. It also includes provisions for improving the health and nutrition of girls by ensuring balanced diet. It also highlights the awareness with regard to make the society aware about the importance of girl education and provide supportive environment for creating a gender just society.

5.3 Silayi Prashikshan Yojna

Under this programme, efforts were made by the Haryana Government to provide training in sewing and related skills to women and girls. The main aim of the scheme is to empower women by enhancing their skills and improve their employability. This scheme helps in equipping women and young girls with sewing skills that will help them in getting employability in garment industry or to start their own small businesses resulting in economic empowerment among girls and women. Under this scheme, participants get certificate after completing their training successfully and also get necessary resources and equipment such as sewing machines, fabrics, and other materials. The scheme also include efforts to raise awareness about the benefits of vocational training and the possibility for the economic empowerment through skill development. The Silayi Prashikshan Yojna is a step towards addressing unemployment and underemployment among women and girls by giving them with important skills resulting in economic opportunities and self-sufficiency.

5.4 Mukhya Mantri Vivah Shagun Yojna

Mukhya Mantri Vivah Shagun Yojna is a scheme to support families for their daughter's marriage. Under this scheme, financial assistance is being provided to the economically disadvantaged families who need help for marriage expenses. Families who belong to low income and fulfill certain socio-economic criteria are eligible to get benefit from this scheme. Under this scheme titled "Mukhya Mantri Vivah Shagun Yojna" is designed to provide financial support to families in Haryana, helping to ease the economic burden of weddings and contributing to the well-being of girls and their families.

5.5 Kishori Shakti Yojana

Kishori Shakti Yojana is a scheme launched by the Government of India, aimed at addressing the needs of adolescent girls in the age group of 11 to 18 years. It focuses on the holistic development of young girls, supporting their health, education, and overall well-being. While this scheme is implemented across various states, including Haryana, it has specific objectives and components designed to empower adolescent girls. The scheme provides nutritional support to adolescent girls to address issues of malnutrition and anemia. This includes the distribution of supplementary nutrition and health check-ups to ensure their physical well-being. Kishori Shakti Yojana promotes educational activities, aiming to improve literacy rates among adolescent girls. It also includes awareness programs on health, hygiene, and life skills. The programme offers vocational training and skill development opportunities to help girls acquire practical skills that enhance their employability and self-reliance. The scheme encourages the participation of girls in community activities and decision-making processes, promoting their social and economic empowerment. It also provides support services such as counseling and guidance on issues related to health, education, and personal development. This helps girls make informed choices and improve their overall quality of life. The scheme is often implemented through Anganwadi centers, which serve as the focal points for delivering various services and programs to the target beneficiaries. This scheme aims to foster the comprehensive development of adolescent girls, equipping them with the knowledge, skills, and resources needed to lead healthy, educated, and empowered lives.

6 Suggestions for empowering adolescent girls

There is a need of life skill education seeing the unique socio-cultural deep-rooted gender disparities in our societies. It also requires a life skills curriculum that enable the adolescents to face the challenges posed by society. This section of the paper provides following suggestions for enhancing life skills education among adolescent girls.

1. There is a need of strengthening community based programmes engaging important stakeholders like parents, local leaders, youth club, Panchayat representatives who need to be made aware about the importance of life skill education.
2. Government policies can play an important role in addressing the challenges related to resource allocation for the development of adolescents. Need of the hour is to allocate funds particularly to rural communities and life skill education should become part of the school curriculum. This includes providing schools with the necessary infrastructure, educational materials, and trained personnel to effectively deliver life skills programs.
3. Teachers in school should also be made aware about the sensitivity of the life skill education. Their focus should not be only completing the syllabus but also provide a platform to the students where they deliver life skills education.
4. Regular monitoring and evaluation should be done on the life skills education programmes in order to assess their effectiveness and impact on the family and community as a whole. This will also help in understanding the gaps and areas for improvement in future plan of action.

Conclusion

Life skills education is a vital component of adolescent development, particularly for rural girls who face significant socio-cultural and economic challenges. Though some initiatives are being taken to include life skill education in school curriculum in urban areas but there is also a need to integrate life skills education in the school curriculum particularly in rural areas. Life skills education can empower adolescent girls to break free from traditional gender roles and achieve their full potential for contributing to the society. It is important to understand the empowering

young girls is not only a subject of particular individual advantage; rather it is vital for creating an fair, prosperous, and sustainable society.

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